

*a non-profit
research institute affiliated with
the University of Bergen*

*Thormøhlensgate 47,
N-5006 Bergen
Norway*

NERSC Technical Report no. 260

*under ESA/NSC PRODEX
contract # 90006*

**MERIS VALIDATION CRUISES IN
THE NORWEGIAN COASTAL CURRENT
DURING SPRING 2002**

UNDER
ENVISAT AO PROJECT # 813

by

**Lasse H. Pettersson, Are Folkestad,
Kai Sørensen and Johnny A. Johannessen**

Bergen, July 13, 2005

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Thormøhlensgate 47

N-5006 Bergen - NORWAY

Phone: +47 55 20 58 00 Fax: +47 55 20 58 01

E-mail: administrasjon@nersc.noWeb.site: <http://www.nersc.no>

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REPORT

TITLE MERIS Validation Cruises in the Norwegian Coastal Current during spring 2002 – under Envisat AO #813	REPORT No. Technical Report no. 260
CLIENT European Space Agency Norwegian Space Centre	CONTRACT No. ESA/NSC PRODEX contract # 90006
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AUTHORS Lasse H. Pettersson, Are Folkestad, Kai Sørensen (NIVA) and Johnny A. Johannessen	DATE July 13, 2005
PROJECT OBJECTIVES : <ul style="list-style-type: none">• To collect sea truth measurements in the Norwegian coastal waters synoptically with Envisat over pass for validation of the MERIS products.• To provide sea truth data to the ESA/NILU database for Envisat products validation.• To perform validation study of the ESA delivered MERIS products with sea truth analysis of core water quality, chlorophyll distribution and other oceanographic parameters.• To perform synergy studies of synoptic MERIS, ASAR and AATSR mapping of the coastal waters.	
APPROVAL Lasse H. Pettersson	Ola M. Johannessen, Director

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1. Main Project Tasks

Brief description of Main Tasks performed according to the contract:

1. Planning of field cruise and data sampling strategy for collection of MERIS validation data in the Norwegian Coastal Current.
2. Rehearse ingestion of field data for inclusion in the ESA/NILU Envisat CalVal database, including participation in ESA preparatory activities for CalVal projects.
3. Completion of a four-week field cruise with R/V Håkon Mosby of the University of Bergen, starting around May 20, 2002 in the area Skagerrak to Stadt, including near real-time analysis and use of Envisat data in the daily planning of the data sampling strategy.
4. Delivery and database ingestion of MERIS CalVal data and cruise report.
5. Post-cruise analysis and reporting of the integrated data from Envisat sensors (MERIS focus but also ASAR and AATSR) and the *in situ* geo-bio-chemical data collected during the validation period.
6. Final project reporting on the MERIS products quality, including synergy use ASAR and AATSR data, in relation to the collected field data from the Norwegian Coastal Current.

2. Introduction

In order to perform validation of the MERIS Level-2 environmental information data products three periods of intensified field data sampling with the R/V Håkon Mosby in the Norwegian Coastal Current have been completed during the late spring and summer period in 2002 (see Figure 1 and Table 1) during the first months after the launch of Envisat. Totally 23 days of field investigations were completed and 73 stations of validation data were collected for on board or post-cruise analysis. The cruises were denoted respectively HM0213, HM0216 and HM0217.

The MERIS marine data products to be validated were the official ESA ground segment MERIS chlorophyll-a (both *algal_1* and *algal_2* products), yellow substances (*yellow_susp*), and Total Suspended Matter (*total_subs*) concentrations. The field data sampling procedures for these parameters were consistent with the protocols derived for MERIS AATSR Validation Team (MAVT). The water samples were usually collected after measurement of the Secchi disk depth and collected at 0 meter, 1/2 Secchi and at Secchi depths. For each station sampled a standard cruise report form were completed and a detailed log were recorded for each water sample collected and preserved (see Annex) for later analysis in the laboratory. This data log contains a wide range of directly and indirectly relevant meteorological and oceanographic information, as well as ge positioning information and other observations. Analysed were the Yellow substance (YS) using a 0.2 µm Nuclepore filter, suspended matter (TSM.DRYW) based on a GFF filter and chlorophyll pigments using HPLC on a 47 mm GFF filter and/or particulate absorption (Chl-a 442 and PBA) on a 24 mm GFF filter. All laboratory analysis of water samples was performed by NIVA (Kai Sørensen and Jo Høkedal). All sampled data were after analysis and quality control ingested in the ESA/NILU Envisat Cal/Val database by NIVA.

In order to perform a holistic validation approach also hydrographical (CTD and Seasoar) and ocean currents data (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler – ADCP) data were collected to describe the near and far field oceanographic situation during the validation cruise periods. To

expand the available amount of satellite ocean colour EO data also the US SeaWiFS data were included and matched-up with the MERIS data originally to be validated.

The acquired data and preliminary validation results has been presented at the MAVT MERIS validation workshop at ESA-ESRIN during December 10-11 2002 and at the Norwegian Space Centre /ESA Prodex meeting in Oslo on January 24th 2003.

The sampled field data are used in publications for validation of both MERIS and SeaWiFS data products as well as for improving bio-optical modelling of Colour Producing Agents (CPA's) in the Norwegian Coastal Current waters.

Figure 1: Station distribution in the Norwegian Coastal Current during the MERIS validation cruises HM0213, HM0216 and HM0217 during spring-summer 2002. Totally 23 days of validation studies were conducted and 73 stations sampled.

Table 1: Summary of the validation cruises and available Envisat MERIS orbits for possible use in this Cal/Val studies.

Date	Orbit #	Lat (°N)	MERIS Status	Comments
Cruise 1: 24 – 29 May 2002				
24-May	1207	60-63.5N		No 1208, but 1207
25-May	1222	60-63.5N		BAD
26-May	1236	60-63.5N	L1/L2	In Skagerak
27-May	1250	60-63.5N		D. Antoine further south
Cruise 2: 27 June – 02 July 2002				
27-Jun	1694	59.5-61.5N	L1/L2	L-2
28-Jun	1708	59.5-61.5N		L-1 no name
29-Jun	1723	59.5-61.5N		L-1 no name
30-Jun	1737	59.5-61.5N		L-1 no name
1-Jul	1751	59.5-61.5N	L1/L2	Resp. L1 / L-2
2-Jul	1766	59.5-61.5N		No/ Bad
Cruise 3: 14 – 18 July 2002				
13-Jul	1923	58-61N	L2	L-2
14-Jul	1937	58-61N	L2	L-2
15-Jul	1952	58-61N		L-1 no name
16-Jul	1966	58-61N		L-1 no name
17-Jul	1980	58-61N	L1/L2	L-1
18-Jul	1995	58-61N		L-1 no name

3. Information Handling and Data Processing

Prior to all cruises a detailed plan for acquisition and ordering of MERIS data were made using the ESOV software (Figure 2, example for the HM0213 cruise). Based on this the daily sampling strategy during the cruises were tuned in order to get possible best match between the in situ sampling and the MERIS coverage in the investigation area. Cloud cover and irregular MERIS operations and acquisitions during the early phase of the Envisat operations were main hampering factors for loss of possible match-up between the in situ and satellite EO data sources. During the validation cruises five days of applicable match-up data were acquired (see Figure 3).

Cruise report forms were generated for all field stations acquired during the three validation cruises in 2002. The forms include information on the validation sampling as well as auxiliary information useful for the data validation and assessment (see Annex). In the following

sections the field data acquired during each of the cruises are presented in tabular form and graphically.

Also optical data were collected during the HM0213 cruise in order to directly validate the water leaving reflectance, and example show in Figure 4 comparing the results of both MERIS and SeaWiFS reflectance validation.

Figure 2: Possible MERIS coverage of coastal Norwegian waters during the HM0213 cruise May 24th to 28th 2002 (the 29th are omitted).

Figure 3: The MERIS algal_2 products shown for the five match-up validation data obtained during the validation cruises in the NCC in 2002.

Figure 4: Comparison of the spectral water leaving reflectance obtained at station number 1, 10 and 11 during HM0213 and the values derived from respectively the MERIS and SeaWiFS images of May 26th.

The colour producing agents (CPA's) and optical measurements were post-processed and systemized for analysis and use in the validation study. Section plots and horizontal surface plots were generated for the CPA's as well as temperature (T-°C) and salinity (S-PSU) has been produced for each section during each of the three cruises. Vertical station plots were generated for the same parameters for each station. A summary of the processed data for each of the cruises HM0123, HM0216 and HM0217 are given in the following sections.

4. Cruise data Report

In the following sections the sampled field data from the validation cruises HM0213, HM0216 and HM0217 are presented by showing tabular information on;

1. Summary of the samplings stations and possible match-up situations
2. Daily assessment off the sampled in situ and satellite data available
3. Summary of the in situ sampling acquired for each station during the cruise

Graphical presentation of the data;

1. Map with station locations
2. Horizontal surface layer (0m) plots of the key in situ parameters sampled (Chl-HPLC, YS, TSM, T and S)
3. Sections plot of the same parameters for the transects made during each cruise, as indicated in Table 3 (map coverage included).
4. Vertical stations plots for each station location of the above in situ parameters.

4.1 Validation Cruise HM0213; 24th – 29th May 2002

Cruise no.	HM0213		Latitude range	60.14 – 63.00 N	
Period:	24. – 29. May 2002		Longitude range	02.04 – 06.21 E	
Sampling stations			Satellite data		
Total no.¹		23		MERIS scenes	SeaWiFS scenes
Matchup MERIS	± 4h	0	No. available	1	5
	total	2			
Matchup SeaWiFS	± 4h	2	No. containing match-ups	1	1
	total	4			
			No. containing match-ups ± 4h	1	1

¹ Total number is showing the number of stations where water samples were taken (for measuring chlorophyll, TSM and YS).

Availability and possible match-ups between satellite images and in situ measurements for cruise HM0213, 24. – 29. May 2002, Norwegian Sea.

HM0213	SeaWiFS			MERIS		
	UTC	Availability	Matchups ¹	UTC	Availability	Matchups ¹
24. May	-	No scenes	-	10:02	1 scene ²	Sta1, Sta2
25. May	13:35	1 scene	None	-	No scenes	-
26. May	12:39	1 scene	Sta8 – Sta11	-	No scenes	-
27. May	11:42 13:20	2 scenes	None	-	No scenes	-
28. May	12:23	1 scene	None	-	No scenes	-
29. May	-	No scenes	-	-	No scenes	-

¹ The term 'matchup' is used for stations that are associated with coordinates showing clear pixels in the satellite image from the same day as the station was visited. The time interval between satellite overpass and water sampling at the 'matchup' stations, may however be too large (several hours) to qualify for a proper matchup following the cal/val protocols.

² MERIS scene from 24. May is received for Level1 products only.

HM0213 Station information

Sta nr	Section	Latitude	Longitude	Date	UTC	Chl ¹	TSM ¹	YS ¹	CTD ²
1	1a	60.1897	5.2364	24. May	16:30		3	3	X
2	1a	60.1425	5.0050	24. May	19:40		2	2	X
3	1b	60.4731	4.2197	25. May	7:40		1	1	X
4	1b	60.4689	4.5333	25. May	9:25		1	1	X
5	1b	60.6358	4.6297	25. May	11:19		1		
6	1b	60.7628	4.8278	25. May	12:39	3	3	3	X
7		62.0836	4.9994	25. May	21:46		2	2	X
8	2	62.2504	4.1655	26. May	1:40		1	1	X
9	2	62.5000	5.0000	26. May	6:30		1	1	X
10	2	62.8322	5.5001	26. May	10:10	3	3	3	X
11	2	63.0022	4.9958	26. May	14:08		1	1	X
12		63.4139	5.3403	27. May	-			1	
13	3	62.8269	6.2103	27. May	9:50	3	6	5	X
14	3	62.8328	5.3336	27. May	15:05		4	4	X
15		62.6161	5.7522	27. May	18:51		1	1	X
16	3	62.8619	4.3103	28. May	1:20		3	3	X
17	4	61.9997	3.4928	28. May	7:08		2	2	X
18	4	61.8742	2.9997	28. May	9:30		1	1	X
19	4	61.7486	2.6681	28. May	10:50	3	3	3	X
20	4	61.5128	2.0358	28. May	14:13		4	4	X
21	5	60.9183	4.4667	29. May	1:44		1	1	
22	5	60.7836	4.1667	29. May	3:17		1	1	
23	5	60.7836	4.6158	29. May	5:30		3	3	X

¹ Number of depths where samples were taken

² X if CTD were sampled

Stations HM0213

HM0213 (Sta 1-23)

Section 1a HM0213 (Sta 1-2)

Section 1b HM0213 (Sta 3-6)

Section 2 (Sta8-11) HM0213

Section 3 HM0213 (Sta 13,14,16)

Section 4 (Sta17-20) HM0213

Section 5 (Sta21-23) HM0213

4.2 Validation Cruise HM0216; 27th June – 2nd July 2002

Cruise no.	HM0216		Latitude range	60.00 – 61.00 N	
Period:	27. June – 2. July 2002		Longitude range	03.33 – 05.33 E	
Sampling stations			Satellite data		
Total no.1	23			MERIS scenes	SeaWiFS scenes
Match-up MERIS	± 4h	1	No. available	2	7
	total	3			
Match-up SeaWiFS	± 4h	7	No. containing match-ups	2	2
	total	12			
			No. containing match-ups ± 4 h	1	2

¹ Total number is showing the number of stations where water samples were taken (for measuring chlorophyll, TSM and YS).

Availability and possible match-ups between satellite images and in situ measurements for cruise HM0216, 27. June – 2. July 2002, Norwegian Sea.

HM0216	SeaWiFS			MERIS		
	UTC	Availability	Matchups ¹	UTC	Availability ²	Matchups ¹
27. June	11:49 13:26	2 scenes	None	10:33	1 scene	Sta167
28. June	12:30	1 scene	Sta170, Sta171	-	No scene	-
29. June	11:33 13:11	2 scenes	None	-	No scene	-
30. June	12:14	1 scene	Sta192 - Sta201	-	No scene	-
01. July	12:55	1 scene	None	10:07	1 scene	Sta202, Sta204
02. July	-	No scene	-	-	No scene	-

¹ The term 'matchup' is used for stations that are associated with coordinates showing clear pixels in the satellite image from the same day as the station was visited. The time interval between satellite overpass and water sampling at the 'matchup' stations, may however be too large (several hours) to qualify for a proper matchup following the cal/val protocols.

² MERIS scenes from 27 June and 1 July are downloaded for Level1 and Level2. However, the Level2 products are not from the latest (August 2003) reprocessing, which is required.

HM0216 Station information

Sta nr	Section	Latitude	Longitude	Date	UTC	Chl ¹	TSM ¹	YS ¹	CTD ²
167	-	60.1664	4.9662	27. June	1915			1	X
168	-	60.1665	4.6655	27. June	-				X
169	-	60.1667	4.3322	27. June	-				X
170	0	60.1028	5.3347	28. June	1030	3	3	3	X
171	0	60.1835	5.1795	28. June	1151	3	3	3	X
172	1a	60.7506	4.6662	29. June	0836	1	3	2	X
173	1a	60.7502	4.5009	29. June	0934	1	3	3	X
174	1a	60.7393	4.7521	29. June	1030	3	3	3	X
175	1a	60.7503	4.3303	29. June	1205				X
176	1a	60.7508	4.1673	29. June	1255				X
177	1a	60.7503	3.9998	29. June	-				X
178	1a	60.7475	3.6667	29. June	1505	1	3	3	X
179	1b	60.4998	3.4993	29. June	-				X
180	1b	60.5000	3.8327	29. June	-				X
181	1b	60.5003	4.1645	29. June	-				X
182	1b	60.5000	4.3332	29. June	-				X
183	1b	60.5000	4.4993	29. June	-				X
184	1b	60.5000	4.6695	29. June	-				X
185	1b	60.5000	4.7198	29. June	-				X
186	1c	60.2492	4.8330	29. June	-				X
187	1c	60.2483	4.6642	30. June	-				X
188	1c	60.2505	4.5003	30. June	-				X
189	1c	60.2505	4.3320	30. June	-				X
190	1c	60.2500	4.1665	30. June	-				X
191	1c	60.2498	3.8337	30. June	-				X
192	1c, 2b	60.2504	3.5011	30. June	0644		3		X
193	1c, 2b	60.2505	3.3330	30. June	0730		3	2	X
194	2a, 2b	60.0741	3.4349	30. June	0920	1	3	3	X
195	2a, 2b	60.0519	3.5439	30. June	1000	3	3	3	X
196	2a, 2b	59.9978	3.7986	30. June	1255	3	3	3	X
197	2a, 2b	59.9996	4.1666	30. June	1436	1	2	2	X
198	2a, 2b	60.0011	4.3370	30. June	1523	1	3	3	X
199	2a, 2b	60.0000	4.6667	30. June	1650	1	3	3	X
200	2a, 2b	59.9833	4.8333	30. June	1824				X
201	2a, 2b	59.9833	4.9167	30. June	1850	1	3	3	X
202	8	60.7506	3.6651	01. July	1016	3	3	3	X
203	8	60.6284	4.2136	01. July	1310	3	3	3	X
204	8	60.5635	4.7500	01. July	1540	1	3	3	X
205	12	60.9997	3.8305	02. July	0224	1	3	3	X
207	12	60.8333	4.3667	02. July	0522	1	3	3	X
208	12	60.7953	4.5211	02. July	0629	1	3	3	X
209	12	60.7505	4.6664	02. July	0724	1	3	3	X

¹ Number of depths where samples were taken

² X if CTD were sampled

HM0216 Sta 170- 209

Section 0 HM0216 (Sta 170 -171)

Section 1 HM0216 (Sta 172 -178)

Section 1b HM0216 (Sta 179 - 185)

Section 1c HM0216 (Sta 186 - 193)

Section 2a HM0216 (Sta 194 -201)

Section 2b HM0216 (Sta 192 -201)

Section 8 HM0216 (Sta 202-204)

Section 12 HM0216 (Sta 205-209)

4.3 Validation Cruise HM0217; 14th – 18th July 2002

Cruise no.	HM0217		Latitude range	58.53 – 60.41 N	
Period:	14. – 18. July 2002		Longitude range	03.33 – 05.58 E	
Sampling stations			Satellite data		
Total no.¹	32			MERIS scenes	SeaWiFS scenes
Match-up MERIS	± 4h	1	No. available	3	5
	total	3			
Match-up SeaWiFS	± 4h	4	No. containing match-ups	2	1
	total	5			
			No. containing match-ups ± 4hr.	1	1

¹ Total number is showing the number of stations where water samples were taken (for measuring chlorophyll, TSM and YS).

Availability and possible matchups between satellite images and in situ measurements for cruise HM0217, 14. – 18. July 2002, Norwegian Sea.

HM0217	SeaWiFS			MERIS		
	UTC	Availability	Matchups ¹	UTC	Availability ²	Matchups ¹
14. July	12:04	1 scene	None	09:59	1 scene ³	Sta 217
15. July	12:45	1 scene	None	-	No scenes	-
16. July	13:26	1 scene	None	-	No scenes	-
17. July	12:30	1 scene	Sta242, Sta245 – Sta248	10:05	1 scene	Sta 247, Sta 248
18. July	13:11	1 scene	None	09:33	1 scene	-

¹ The term 'matchup' is used for stations that are associated with coordinates showing clear pixels in the satellite image from the same day as the station was visited. The time interval between satellite overpass and water sampling at the 'matchup' stations, may however be too large (several hours) to qualify for a proper matchup following the cal/val protocols.

² MERIS scene from 14. July is downloaded for Level1 and Level2. However, the Level2 products are not from the latest (August 2003) reprocessing, which is required. The scene from 17. July is received only for Level1 products. The scene from 18. July is available in the ENVISAT Catalogue but is not yet downloaded (02. Oct. 2003).

³ The MERIS scene from 14. July is not covering the whole area of cruise stations from this date. Stations 218, 219 and Station A are not covered by the scene.

HM0217 Station information

Sta nr	Section	Latitude	Longitude	Date	UTC	Chl ¹	TSM ¹	YS ¹	CTD ²
217	5	60.1669	4.8348	14. July	09:44	1	3	3	X
218	5	60.1649	4.5018	14. July	11:30	1		3	X
219	5	60.1679	4.1666	14. July	13:05	1		3	X
A	5	60.1663	3.5425	14. July	19:00			BP	
B	6	59.0000	3.5000	15. July	04:15			BP	
C	6	59.0000	4.0267	15. July	06:15			BP	
220	6	59.0033	4.4650	15. July	08:05	1		3	X
221	6	59.0017	4.8767	15. July	10:01	3	3	3	X
222	6, 7	58.9977	5.3176	15. July	11:56	1		3	X
223	7	58.7546	5.3330	15. July	14:07	1		3	X
224	7	58.6891	5.0021	15. July	15:49				X
225	-	58.4872	5.2938	16. July	-				X
226	8	58.5333	5.5778	16. July	05:45	1		1	X
227	8	58.6236	5.3088	16. July	07:10	1		1	X
228	8	58.7132	5.0385	16. July	08:30	1		1	X
229	8	58.8010	4.7665	16. July	09:49	1	2	3	X
230	8	58.8904	4.4937	16. July	11:15			1	X
231	8	58.9771	4.2200	16. July	12:35			1	X
232	8	59.0628	3.9438	16. July	13:58			1	X
233	8	59.1493	3.6650	16. July	15:28			1	X
234	8, 10	59.2533	3.3358	16. July	17:05			1	X
235	10	59.2508	3.6652	16. July	18.25			1	X
236	10	59.2513	4.0002	16. July	19:45			1	X
237	10	59.2502	4.3332	16. July	21:09			1	X
238	10	59.2632	4.7377	16. July	23:35			1	X
239	12	59.4987	4.7470	17. July	-				X
240	12	59.4910	4.4215	17. July	-				X
241	12, 14	59.7500	4.3338	17. July	05:41	1		1	X
242	14	59.7517	4.6683	17. July	07:05	1		1	X
243	14	59.7503	4.9138	17. July	08:30	1		1	X
244	14, 15	59.6667	4.8333	17. July	09:20	2	3	3	X
245	15	59.4992	4.0000	17. July	12:46	1		1	X
246	15	59.4983	3.7988	17. July	13:58	1		1	X
247	15	59.4988	3.4745	17. July	15:20	1		1	X
248	15	59.5017	3.3323	17. July	16.02	1		1	X
249	16	59.7502	3.3335	17. July	-				X
250	16	59.7500	3.6665	17. July	-				X
251	16	59.7503	3.9997	17. July	-				X
252	-	60.4103	5.2778	18. July	10:45	2	3	3	

¹ Number of depths where samples were taken

² X if CTD were sampled

Stations HM0217

Section 5 HM0217 (Sta 217 -219, A)

Section 6 HM0217 (Sta B, C, 220 - 222)

Section 7 HM0217 (Sta 222-224)

Section 8 HM0217 (Sta 226 - 234)

Section 10 HM0217 (Sta 234 - 238)

Section 12 HM0217 (Sta 239 - 241)

Section 14 HM0217 (Sta 241 - 244)

Section 15 HM0217 (Sta 244 - 248)

Section 16 HM0217 (Sta 249 - 251)

Chl. hplc [mg/m³]

YS [m⁻¹]

TSM [g/m³]

5. ANNEX: Station form used during MERIS-validation cruises

Station #:		Location name:	Vessel	Håkon Mosby
Position:				
Date:		Arrival UTC:		
Air temp.:		Barometer:		Hygrometer % RH
Wind speed:		Wind direction:		
Wave height:		Wave direction:	Wave type:	
Visibility:		Cloud-cover:	Surface material:	

Secchi	UTC	White	Green	Blue	Red	Black
Sun						
Shadow						

CTD	File:	UTC:	
Water sample	Secchi depth:	1/2 Secchi depth	Surface
Depth (m):			
UTC:			

AC9	UTC:	File:	
Hydroscat	UTC:	File:	
Ed	UTC:	File:	
Eu	UTC:	File:	
Edekk	UTC:	File;	

Secchi	UTC	White	UTC	White	UTC	White
Sun						
Shadow						

END of STATION

Station:		Location name:	Vessel	Håkon Mosby
Position:				
Date:		Departure UTC:		
Air temp.:		Barometer:		Hygrometer % RH
Wind speed:		Wind direction:		
Wave height:		Wave direction:	Wave type:	
Visibility:		Cloud-cover:	Surface material:	

Save copy				
Form	CTD	BB6	AC9	PRR

Water sample / filtration (volumes)

Station	Depth	YS /TSM (0.2 microns)	TSM	CHL HPLC	CHL abs.	Comments